

Methodology for creating a Dynamic Material Passport Application, powered by Microsoft Power Apps and ChatGPT for Circular Built Environment

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Abstract

Material Passports (MPs) are crucial for promoting Circular Economy (CE) in the Built Environment (BE), but existing systems face challenges due to their static nature. This paper describes the methodological approach used for creating a Dynamic Material Passports (DMPs) App using Microsoft Power Apps and AI functionalities powered by ChatGPT. The app improves material data management, lifecycle assessments, and geospatial mapping by offering real-time updates and automated access to current material information. The DMPs integrates with external databases, such as the 2050-Materials Database, and enhances decision-making by providing AI-driven insights. QR-code-enabled geospatial tools support lifecycle assessments by linking material data to geographic locations. Validity and reliability are ensured through a triangulation approach, combining literature reviews, case studies, stakeholder feedback, and pilot testing. The DMPs framework fosters circular economy practices, promoting material reuse and recycling while supporting sustainable decision-making in the built environment.

1. Introduction

This research employs a pragmatism paradigm, utilizing a mixed-methods approach to create a DMPs interface tool aimed at advancing material lifecycle management within the built BE. Pragmatism, as a research philosophy, allows for the integration of both quantitative and qualitative methodologies, providing the flexibility to explore complex, real-world problems and offer actionable, practical solutions (Abiodun and Egbu, 2018). The research leverages Building Information Modelling (BIM)-enabled processes, which are aligned with ISO 19650 standards to ensure a structured and standardized approach to data management. Through BIM, the study integrates data from material inventories and conducts comprehensive Lifecycle Assessments (LCA), aiming to minimize carbon footprints and reduce the environmental impact of construction materials (Çetin, Straub, et al., 2022; Honic et al., 2019)

In addition, the methodology places a strong emphasis on stakeholder involvement, ensuring that the developed DMP framework is robust, relevant, and adaptable to the needs of industry professionals. By engaging stakeholders throughout the process, the research ensures that the framework remains applicable and useful in real-world contexts, facilitating its integration into current practices. This methodology not only addresses the technical development of the DMP but also integrates the philosophical foundations of

pragmatism, ensuring that the final framework is both theoretically sound and environmentally sustainable, with real-world applicability.

2. Research Philosophy

2.1 Research Approaches

Research methodologies are typically classified into three main categories: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods. Each of these approaches offers distinct advantages and is selected based on the nature of the research questions. Qualitative research focuses on understanding phenomena from a contextual and subjective perspective. This approach explores complex concepts through the analysis of textual data, interviews, and observations (Creswell, 2007, 2009). Therefore, a literature review is important for reviewing the current state of MP frameworks, understanding barriers to adoption, and exploring how digital tools, such as BIM, influence CE construction practices. On the other hand, Quantitative research, in contrast, relies on numerical data and statistical analysis to validate hypotheses. It is used to measure variables, establishing patterns, relationships, or causality (Creswell, 2007, 2009). In this research, quantitative techniques are applied to assess material lifecycle data, carbon emissions, and other performance metrics associated with the integration of DMPs. Lastly, mixed methods research combines both qualitative and quantitative techniques, offering a more comprehensive understanding of research problems (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). By utilising this approach, the research benefits from the strengths of both methodologies, ensuring that subjective insights are supported by empirical data. The mixed-methods approach is a natural fit with the pragmatism paradigm, providing flexibility and adaptability necessary for addressing real-world challenges in construction.

2.2 Ontology, Epistemology, and Axiology

The ontological stance of this research is grounded in critical realism. Critical realism recognizes the existence of a material world while acknowledging that our understanding of it is influenced by social and cultural contexts (Abiodun and Egbu, 2018). This ontological perspective is crucial in addressing complex construction processes, where subjective interpretations coexist with objective realities. This approach is especially relevant when dealing with DMPs because it allows for a nuanced understanding that considers both measurable material data and the social implications of material use.

In terms of epistemological view, the study adopts relativism, which emphasizes that knowledge is shaped by the researcher's beliefs and biases (Oppong, 2014). This epistemological position allows for a comprehensive understanding of DMPs by incorporating diverse stakeholder perspectives. Relativism ensures that the research remains flexible and adaptive to new findings, enabling a more nuanced exploration of material circularity. By embracing relativism, the study captures the multifaceted nature of knowledge, integrating both technical data and human experiences.

Finally, the axiological stance of this study is embedded in the pragmatist tradition, which focuses on solving real-world problems, such as reducing CO₂ emissions in the construction sector (Abiodun and Egbu, 2018). The pragmatist approach to axiology prioritizes research outcomes that deliver tangible societal benefits. The study emphasizes environmental sustainability, resource conservation, and operational efficiency as key values driving the development of DMPs. This focus ensures that the research provides solutions with real-world applicability, offering substantial value beyond academic discourse.

2.3 Research Paradigm

The pragmatism paradigm has been selected due to its problem-solving nature and its suitability for applied research (Cameron, 2010). Pragmatism allows for the use of multiple methods to address practical challenges in construction, encouraging stakeholder engagement for continuous improvement (Abiodun and Egbu, 2018; Feilzer, 2010). This paradigm ensures a seamless integration of theoretical frameworks and practical applications, ultimately enhancing ecological efficacy and resource conservation (Cameron, 2010). Pragmatism also encourages iterative development, making it highly adaptable to the evolving regulatory environment of the construction industry. This adaptability is essential for the successful implementation of DMPs, which must adhere to emerging sustainability standards. The pragmatic focus on actionable outcomes ensures that the research findings are not only theoretically sound but also practically implementable. Moreover, pragmatism bridges the gap between knowledge and action, facilitating the creation of innovative and feasible solutions.

3. Research Design

3.1 Primary Research

The primary research centres on the development of a DMP interface using Microsoft Power Apps. The interface will incorporate AI-powered features, such as ChatGPT and Microsoft Copilot, for real-time data retrieval and interpretation (Markou et al., 2025). This system is designed to integrate BIM models in IFC format, supporting real-time synchronisation with platforms like Autodesk Revit (Stella et al., 2023). The user-friendly nature of Microsoft Power Apps ensures that the interface is accessible to industry professionals, thereby promoting the widespread adoption of the DMPs framework.

BIM is central to the research design, ensuring compliance with ISO 19650 standards. During RIBA Stages 2 and 3, BIM models will incorporate generic material data sourced from the Irish Green Building Council (IGBC, 2025). At the technical design stage, detailed material data will be dynamically integrated from the 2050-Materials database through API connections (Markou et al., 2025). By integrating BIM in this way, the research guarantees consistent management of material data throughout the project lifecycle, enabling accurate environmental assessments and facilitating informed decision-making. The BIM-based approach serves as a digital representation of the building lifecycle, enabling the tracking of material flows and environmental impacts from the inception of a project to its demolition. The integration of BIM at various stages ensures a holistic approach to material management, aligning the research with industry best practices.

The proposed DMPs system employs two key components:

- **Generic Material Passports:** These are sourced from the IGBC inventory for early-stage material assessments. These passports provide foundational data essential for preliminary sustainability evaluations.
- **Specific Material Passports:** Integrated from the 2050-Materials database (2050-Materials, 2025), these passports offer detailed data on material properties, lifecycle classification, and embodied carbon data. The inclusion of specific material passports ensures that the DMP system remains relevant throughout later stages of construction, providing in-depth insights necessary for advanced environmental impact analyses.

This dual approach, by employing both generic and specific material passports, ensures the flexibility of the framework. It supports early-stage design decisions while providing detailed data for later-stage technical development. This adaptability enhances the framework’s relevance across a wide range of construction projects.

The environmental effects of building elements can be evaluated through the incorporation of LCA, in accordance with ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards, evaluating Scope 1, 2, and 3 emissions. Real-time LCA calculations are embedded in the DMP interface, allowing stakeholders to make fact-based decisions aimed at reducing carbon footprints (Stella et al., 2023). The use of standardized LCA frameworks ensures comparability across projects, enabling stakeholders to benchmark performance and implement best practices effectively. The LCA methodology covers cradle-to-grave assessments, considering emissions during material extraction, transportation, construction, and end-of-life disposal. By including these comprehensive assessments, the research promotes a circular economy approach, minimizing waste and environmental impact.

Access to the DMP app can be facilitated through QR codes embedded on construction materials, enabling instant retrieval of material data via smartphones or tablets. These QR codes link directly to the DMP interface, providing real-time information on material properties, lifecycle data, and sustainability metrics. By scanning the QR code, users will not only gain access to comprehensive material data but also obtain geolocation information for real-time material tracking. This feature further enables the automation of Global Warming Potential (GWP) calculations related to transportation, enhancing accuracy in carbon footprint assessments and supporting sustainable logistics management (Markou et al., 2024, 2025). Figure 1 shows the workflow of the proposed DMPs framework.

Figure 1: The proposed framework of DMPs

3.2 Primary Data Sources

Key primary data sources include:

- Material Inventories: The IGBC and 2050-Materials databases provide both foundational and detailed material data.
- BIM Models: Developed in line with ISO 19650, ensuring adherence to global best practices in digital construction processes.
- Pilot Case Study: This study evaluates the practical applicability and scalability of the framework.
- Madaster Collaboration: This collaboration validates the framework by benchmarking it against industry standards (Markou et al., 2025). Madaster's involvement adds external credibility, enhancing the robustness of the research.

3.3 Secondary Data Sources

A comprehensive literature review constitutes a vital part for identifying trends and gaps in current state of MPs frameworks. This review focuses on MPs, BIM, CE principles, and sustainability practices (Çetin, Gruis, et al., 2022; Çetin, Straub, et al., 2022). Regulatory frameworks such as the European Sustainable Product Regulation (ESPR) 2024 are analysed to ensure compliance with evolving sustainability standards. Furthermore, environmental impact assessments are performed using standardized methods developed by the Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors (RICS). Incorporating diverse secondary data ensures that the research is firmly rooted in both academic theory and industry practice. The literature review also highlights best practices and case studies from various geographical contexts, enriching the research framework with diverse insights. This global perspective ensures that the DMP framework can be adapted to different regulatory and market environments.

4. Analysis of data

The analysis utilizes both qualitative and quantitative methods:

- Qualitative Analysis: Thematic analysis of stakeholder feedback and content analysis of literature to identify industry trends and gaps in methodology. This analysis provides context-specific insights that inform the development of the framework.
- Quantitative Analysis: LCA for environmental impact measurement, statistical analysis for sustainability indicators, and geospatial analysis for regional performance assessment (Honic et al., 2019b) The quantitative approach provides empirical evidence to support the qualitative findings, resulting in a well-rounded research outcome.

4.1 Software and Tools

The study utilises a robust suite of tools:

- BIM Tools: Autodesk Revit for model creation and analysis, ensuring compliance with ISO 19650 standards.
- Microsoft Power Apps: For DMP interface development, providing a user-friendly, low-code platform.

- 2050-Materials API Integration: Facilitates real-time data synchronization with external databases, improving data accuracy and reliability.
- Power BI and Excel: These tools are used for data analysis and visualization, presenting complex data clearly.
- OpenGIS: For geospatial mapping, providing spatial analysis to support lifecycle assessments.
- Madaster: For benchmarking and validating the framework, ensuring compliance with industry standards (Markou et al., 2025).

4.2 Validity and Reliability

Reliability is maintained through triangulation, combining literature reviews, case studies, and modelling. The DMP framework is validated through Madaster benchmarking and pilot case studies. Detailed documentation of data collection and analysis procedures ensures reproducibility and transparency. Using multiple validation techniques strengthens the credibility of the research, ensuring that the findings are both reliable and applicable in real-world settings.

4.3 Ethical Considerations

The research adheres to ethical standards, including GDPR compliance, ensuring data privacy and confidentiality. Data is anonymized and securely stored, with explicit consent obtained for its use. Findings are presented transparently, with methods and results shared openly to ensure reproducibility and integrity. Ethical considerations are embedded throughout the research process, ensuring compliance with both academic and industry standards.

5. Conclusion

This methodology presents a robust framework for developing BIM-based Dynamic Material Passports, guided by pragmatism and a mixed-methods design. By integrating advanced technologies, adhering to international standards, and ensuring rigorous validation, the research contributes significantly to sustainable practices in the built environment. It not only offers a comprehensive approach to material lifecycle management but also provides a scalable model that can be adapted to various construction projects, promoting long-term sustainability and resource conservation. The approach outlined in this methodology underscores the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration, robust data management, and continuous validation in achieving the goals of sustainability and circular economy within the construction industry.

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